

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Promotion of soil fauna in wheat cultivation in the continental region - clover undersowing vs. biostimulant

Promoting a diverse soil fauna is an important aspect of ensuring sustainable agricultural production on healthy soils. Two measures that appear promising in this context are the use of undersowing and the application of biostimulants. While biostimulants are intended to increase the root growth of crops, undersowing introduces an additional root system into the soil. A positive influence on the soil fauna can be expected due to the larger rhizosphere and the higher food quantity (more root exudates and microorganisms). This potential is also confirmed by case studies from wheat cultivation in the continental region. The effects of undersowing clover and a biostimulant combined with a plant adjuvant (based on rhizosphere microorganisms and algae extracts) were investigated with a simultaneous reduction

in plant protection products. A positive effect of both measures on the soil fauna could be demonstrated in the following year. In direct comparison, the clover undersowing showed a higher potential for promoting soil fauna. It resulted in a significant increase in earthworm biomass, collembolan abundance, species number and diversity as well as mite abundance and the number of functional groups within the mite community. Although the application of the biostimulant had a positive effect on the number and diversity of collembolan species, it had no effect on the earthworm and mite community. As a targeted measure to promote soil biodiversity, undersowing therefore has a broader range of positive effects.

1. Earthworm extraction on an experimental field.

2. Undersown clover between wheat plants.

KEYWORDS

Clover undersowing, biostimulant, soil fauna

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